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Assessing the Representativeness of Main Paths by Their Coverage¹

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Introduction

Main path analysis (MPA) (Hummon & Dorian, 1989) is popular among researchers of diversified disciplines. A quick check on Google Scholar using the term “main path analysis” returns more than 380 articles just after 2021. These articles’ publication by esteemed journals like *Scientometrics*, *Journal of Informetrics*, *Technology Forecasting and Social Changes* suggests that MPA is well received in the field of scientometrics. MPA is also immediately available from the renowned network analysis software Pajek (Batagelj & Mrvar, 1998; De Nooy, Mrvar, & Batagelj, 2018).

MPA is commonly applied to a network of papers or patents from a research or technology field interconnected by their citations. This citation network may be considered as embodying a knowledge system for the field. MPA then derives from the network one or more series of end-to-end connected arcs, called *main paths* (MPs), as representative trajectories epitomizing how the knowledge system evolves.

MPA provides a significant reduction to the network of documents, and it is quite common that, from tens of thousands of documents, only a small number of them are retained in the one or more derived MPs. To give a few examples from some recent works, Su, Chen, Lu, and Huang (2021) obtained a MP involving 22 out of 3,193 academic papers from the field of augmented reality. Yu and Sheng (2021), from a network of 2,233 supply chain finance papers, derived MPs of 26, 24, 24, and 31 papers respectively using algorithms. Kuan, Chen, and Huang (2020), from 31,071 patents and pre-grant publications, discovered a MP of 71 documents. According

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to these works, their MPs achieve a reduction ratio (i.e., no of nodes along the MPs divided by the total number of nodes of the network) ranging from 0.23% to 1.39%.

Given the significant reduction of MPA, a question inevitably arises: how representative the MPs are in epitomizing the network of documents. This is a difficult question as the answer involves issues related to the soundness of the document retrieval strategy, how the citation network is constructed, which algorithms are most appropriate in reflecting knowledge flow, etc.

Researchers generally resort to two approaches in settling the MP authenticity issue. On one hand, they often contrast the MPs against the related field's development, claiming that the MPs indeed reflect what the field undergoes in the real world. On the other hand, they rely on some bibliometric measures, such as centrality, to suggest that the documents along the MPs are indeed of great significance to the fields' knowledge development.

The present study is aimed to address the representative issue of MPs, and is motivated by the authors' noticing that the MPs may be attributed to only a portion of nodes of the network. Based on this understanding, a quantitative measure is proposed by the present study.

Weight Assignment in MPA

The gist of MPA lies in two ingredients: weight assignment and path discovery. There are various weight assignment algorithms and the three most common ones, *search path count* (SPC) (Batagelj, 2003), *search path link count* (SPLC), and *search path node pair* (SPNP) (both from Hummon and Doreian (1989)) assign a weight to each arc based on how many times it is traversed between various pairs of nodes. There are also various path discovery algorithms, which all identify one or more MPs between the network's source and sink nodes based on the arc weights.

The arcs constituting the MPs are identified solely with their weights. The weights of these arcs, and therefore the entire MPs, may be attributed to only a portion of the citation network. In other words, the MPs may only account for or *cover* this portion of the citation network. The representativeness of the MPs, therefore, may be objectively assessed by how much the citation network is covered by the MPs.

To see what attributes to an arc's weight, the three most popular weight assignment algorithms, i.e., SPC, SPLC, and SPNP, are examined. The arc's SPC, SPLC, or SPNP weight is based on the number of times an arc is crossed between two sets of nodes, and these algorithms differ only in the sets of nodes they involve.

There are four sets of nodes that are respectively considered by SPC, SPLC, and SPNP for an arc (s, t): (1) the source nodes that may cross the arc (s, t) to reach the terminal node t, (2) the sink nodes that may be reached from the start node s after crossing (s, t), (3) all nodes preceding (s, t) that may cross (s, t) to reach t, and (4) all succeeding nodes that may be reached from s after crossing (s, t).

An arc's SPC weight is determined only by the source and sink nodes. SPLC considers preceding nodes, not just the source nodes, to the arc, as well as the sink nodes. SPNP, in addition to the preceding nodes, further considers the succeeding nodes, not only the sink nodes, of the arc. As a demonstration, Figure 1 depicts a fictitious network whose nodes are numbered from 1 to 13, and arc weights are respectively assigned by SPNP. The main paths of the

networks include the dark arcs connecting the black nodes. Using the arc (8, 12) as an example, the preceding nodes 1~4 may reach the arc twice, and the preceding nodes 5~8 reaches the arc only once. So, the arc's preceding nodes may totally reach the arc 12 times. As the arc only involves a single succeeding node 12, its SPNP weight is 12 (=12x1).

Figure 1: A fictitious network whose arc weights are assigned by SPNP.

The Coverage of MPs

As explained above, the weight of an arc (s, t), whether it is by SPC, SPLC, SPNP, or an algorithm also based on its traversal count, is attributed to the nodes that may *reach* or may be *reached* by the arc following one or more paths. In other words, the nodes not preceding s and those not succeeding t would not affect its weight at all.

Figure 2 depicts a portion of a citation network where the MPs involve the black nodes. As illustrated, the grey nodes are those cannot reach the MPs but may be reached by at least a node of the MPs. The patterned nodes are those that may reach at least one node of the MPs but not the other way around. One of the patterned nodes, node 15, is reachable to and from to at least one node of the MPs. The white nodes cannot reach the nodes of the MPs and vice versa. These white nodes do not precede or succeed any MP arc and, with or without them, the weights of the MP arcs remain the same. In other words, these nodes are irrelevant to the MPs.

Figure 2: A portion of a citation network.

As explained above, the MPs can only account for, or cover the nodes preceding and succeeding the MP arcs. Then, these nodes and their interconnecting arcs, collectively referred to as the *coverage set* or *coverage* of the MP, which is a sub-network (V_{CS}, E_{CS}) to the citation network (V, E) . The MPs also constitute a sub-network (V_{MP}, E_{MP}) , where $V_{MP} \subset V_{CS} \subset V$ and $E_{MP} \subset E_{CS} \subset E$.

Then, a degree of representativeness of the MPs can be quantitatively measured by the share of the network's nodes that are covered by the MP, referred to as the MP's *coverage ratio* defined as $|V_{CS}|/|V|$.

The coverage ratio of the MPs provides an assessment to how trustworthy the documents along the MPs are in revealing their field's knowledge evolution. MPs having a coverage ratio equal or close to one can be said to fully represent its citation network and, as all or nearly all documents of the fields are accounted for, these documents can be considered to fully reflect the field's evolution. On the other hand, with a coverage ratio close to zero, the citation network may be considered ill represented by the MPs and whether the documents along the MP constitute the field's evolution trajectory would be dubious.

It should be pointed that a citation network often consists of a number of components and some prior MPA-related works indicated that their MPs are derived from the most significant components as a hint to the trustworthiness of their MPs. However, as explained above, the MPs derived from the most significant components do not guarantee their representativeness.

Future Work

This study pointed out that some nodes of a citation network are irrelevant to the derived MPs. As such, a degree of representativeness of the MPs can be quantitatively measured by the MP's coverage ratio. As to the nodes outside the coverage of the MPs, the authors plan to develop a method to identify these nodes, extract them as a new network, and apply MPA to discover auxiliary MPs from the new network. This identify-extract-analyze process may be repeated iteratively until all nodes of the network are covered and, as such, all possible MPs from the network are exhaustively discovered.

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